

Theories of Justice, Profane and Prophetic: Scholem on the Bolshevik Revolution

by
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Gershom Scholem, *The Bolshevik Revolution* [1918]
(Translated from the German by Eric Jacobson)

Bolshevism has a central idea which lends magic to its movement: the messianic kingdom can only unfold in the dictatorship of poverty. (Perhaps the error is that it cannot unfold in itself – which is Tolstoyism. This serious confusion brought so many of Tolstoy's followers to the movement). Because of this, only the judgement of the impoverished has revolutionary power. The poor may not be just but they can never be unjust. Poverty, even where it is dictatorial, is not *Gewalt* [authority/violence]. Moscow's theory of the firing squad appears as an ethical outcome: the unjust kingdom stands trial. Bolshevism is the attempt to stand divine judgement on its head. It kills in the name of a mission.

Revolution exists where the messianic kingdom is to be established without the teachings. For this reason, there can be no revolution for the Jews. The Jewish revolution has to be reconnected to the teachings. A revolution that is clearly based on the messianic kingdom, like the Bolshevik or French revolution, must be distinguished principally from the frail pseudo-revolutions that are centered on "progress", like Germany in 1848. The messianic kingdom, the eternal now of history, cannot be reached gradually. Liberalism is a conforming imitation of messianism that functions by a rule of operation. In key moments, it is extended indefinitely and thus loses its conformity. Asymptotes are the guidelines of liberalism. The circle turns from hyperbole to the imaginary.

Revolutions fail. But this is not, nor can it ever be, an argument against them. Revolutions convey time and again the silent teachings of the unambiguity of history.

* This essay is dedicated to David Hitchin.

[Gershom Scholem: *In memoriam*, 2 (Jerusalem Studies in Jewish Thought, 21), 2007]

Intrinsically, the Bolshevik revolution, like every legitimate revolution, has a double point in which *Gewalt* emerges through the inner collision of structures (which must appear due to the exclusion of the Torah).

The great historical paradox put forward is that exactly where poverty reigns, it remains poverty nonetheless – as if the faithfulness of the poor to poverty would be the only and highest guarantee of the Bolshevik idea. Is this possible or sensible? Such a system would be revolutionary consistency – an absolute, self-sustaining system. And precisely because revolutions, unlike liberalism, lack a form of consistency understood in this sense, they fail.

Anatole France, in his book, *La révolte des anges*, sets a limit for the idea of the teachings with ironic necessity. His true, deep, and perhaps unutterable question is: how can one overcome the prescriptive circular reasoning of revolution? He does not answer the question. But true mysticism can, which considers circular reasoning a legitimate, fundamental idea.

Even though the Bolshevik revolution will be caught up in bloodshed (and the miraculous thing about it is the very fact that it will not drown in its own blood), it will nevertheless serve as the only high-point of the history of the world war and, however saddening this may be, the messianic reaction against it. Zionism has nothing in common with the world war, from which it turns away without response. Whoever affirms the history has to be a Bolshevik, seeing in it the futuristic and purest form of the present in blood and misdeed.

One might be able to designate revolutionary actions as those distinguishable from both the ordinary and historical in that they are conducted in good faith while standing in the face of history. The person who knows that he is acting historically, is revolutionary. Yet Bolshevism does more than this: it acts not only conscious of standing in the face of history, it seeks at the same time to act futurist in a specific sense. But with action, this is not simultaneously possible. Bolshevism tries – perhaps with grandeur but surely for naught – to suspend judgement over itself through the permanence of its singular point of *Gewalt* which appears to itself as the future it anticipates. For this reason, it is unjust, and the root of its reprehensibility is independent of its position on spirituality and labor.¹

1 Gershom Scholem, *Tagebücher, nebst Aufsätzen und Entwürfen bis 1923*, Band I, 1913–1917, ed. Karlfried Gründer and Friedrich Niewöhner. Frankfurt: Jüdischer Verlag,